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Classification of hygienic factors affecting the morbidity of school-aged children

K.I. Ibrahimov

Bukhara State Medical Institute general hygiene assistant

Annotation

"According to new data from the WHO, nine out of ten people breathe air with high levels of pollutants, and according to the latest estimates, 7 million people die each year from air and indoor air pollution. a person dies[WHO, 2023].

According to WHO data, more than 494,000 new cases of the disease were recorded in the world during the last day.

Air quality for WHO member states to improve epidemiological control of all air pollution-related diseases, conduct scientific research on the health effects of air pollution, and implement the "WHO Recommendations on Indoor Air Quality" It is not without reason that he recommends the creation of monitoring systems and health registers.

Key words. Lesson schedule, mental development, growth and development.

In the 2023-2024 academic year, there are 10,163 schools in our country, where 6,476,091 students study, while in Bukhara region, 326,112 students study in 534 schools, of the total number of children is 6.8%.

Research results.

There are 54 schools in Shafirkon district, and our research was conducted in 18-29 secondary schools in Shafirkon district.

Mental and physical development of students during the day and during the lesson depends on internal school factors, microclimate indicators of the classrooms, ensuring constant high efficiency of working ability, organization of classes based on hygienic requirements.

The workload of students during the day and week depends on the physiological high and low days of their working ability and the level of complexity of the lessons.

The most productive days of the week are Wednesday and Thursday, and the lowest days are Monday and Saturday (9,10).

At the school, Saturday is designated as a day off for primary classes. A 5-day work schedule has been approved for elementary grades, and 6 days for middle and high grades.

Table 1 shows the structure of the class schedule and the level of complexity of the lessons.

Color distribution of study hours depending on the level of complexity during the days of the week in grades 5-9 (in points)

		18 schools				29 schools		
Days of the week and class (in hours)		5 A	6 A	9 A	9 B	5 A	6 A	9 A
Monday	1	9	3	5	9	10	11	9
	2	4	12	9	10	9	6	7
	3	10	8	7	6	2	8	2
	4	10		9	7	3	13	7
	5	8	13	10	5			9
	6				7			7
	7							
Total		41	36	40	44	24	38	41
Tuesday	1	0	13	6	12		8	7

	2	10	11	8	10	10	11	7
	3	3	6	10	8	3	12	5
	4	5	10	12	7	5	3	8
	5	8	8	11	7	8		3
	6			7	11			9
Total		26	48	47	55	26	34	43
Wednesday	1	9	13	6	9	9	8	8
	2	10	11	8	7	10	13	5
	3	2	8	10	5	2	6	10
	4	4	4	12	13	4	4	7
	5	4	11	11	7	4	12	13
	6			7	7			9
Total		29	47	54	48	29	33	52
Thursday	1	9	3	7	12	9	12	6
	2	3	11	12	7	3	10	8
	3	4	13		7	4	13	2
	4	5	6	8	7	5	11	7
	5	9	8	7	2	9	8	8
	6			2	8			7
Total		29	41	36	43	30	44	38
Friday	1			2	3			
	2	9	13	2	9	9	1	7
	3	10	1	2	7	10	4	13
	4	4	12	2	8	4	3	12
	5	4	11	2	6	4	13	
	6				9		11	
Total		27	37	10	42	27	32	32
Saturday	1	10	8		2	10	11	6
	2	9	3	7	2	9	13	12
	3	8	12	10	2	8	11	7
	4	3	11	4	2	3	3	9
	5			9	2		8	7
	6						4	
Total		30	33	31	10	30	50	41

In 5 "A" classes of 18 secondary schools, the difficulty level of lessons on Monday was 41 points, the 1st and 2nd lessons were given lessons with a weight of 10 points, which does not fully meet the hygienic requirements. .

The total complexity level of daily downloads on Tuesday was 26 points.

The sum of the total points of the lessons on Wednesdays of the week was 29 points, and the sum of the points of the lessons on Thursday was 30 points. On Thursday, it is necessary to replace the first lesson with the 5th lesson.

Lesson 5 on Friday is unevenly distributed according to the level of difficulty, and the total score is 30 points.

On Saturday, the total weight is 30 points, and the subject in lessons 1-2, which is difficult to master, should be moved to Wednesday or Thursday of the week.

5 In "B" class, on the days of the week when the above situations were observed, the scores were 36-48-47-41-37-33 on Monday, while on Monday, the 2nd-5th lessons were placed irregularly in the lesson schedule. This in turn causes students to be tired from the beginning of the week[2,4].

6 "A" on Monday, the level of complexity of general lessons was 36 points, which does not meet hygienic requirements at all. If the complex lessons of the 3rd and 4th hours on Saturday are not changed to other days of the week, the students' ability to work will be reduced and the dynamic and statistical components of the lessons will be lost[3].

9 The level of complexity of "A" classes was 40-47-54-36-10-31 points. On Friday, the daily load consists of 5 lessons and there are a number of shortcomings in the sequence. It is necessary to replace the third lesson on Saturday with other hours.

9 In "B" class, the level of complexity of Monday's lessons is 44 points, and in the 1st and 2nd lessons, complex lessons of 9 and 10 points are set, which is

completely contrary to hygienic requirements. On Tuesday, only difficult lessons were given, and the sum total of the daily difficulty level was 55 points. On the days of the week with high working capacity, the distribution of loads is not based on the current sanitary regulations. Physical education classes on Saturday[1,2].

It is worth noting that the rough changes on Mondays and Saturdays of the week in this class cause changes in children's functional state, especially in their mental system, in the transition period of this age, not only in subjects, but also in their general interests. will be

In 5 "A" classes out of 29 schools, the level of complexity of lessons on Monday was 24 points, the 1st and 2nd lessons were given lessons with a weight of 10 points, which does not fully meet the hygienic requirements.

The total complexity level of daily downloads on Tuesday was 26 points.

The sum of the total points of the lessons on Wednesdays of the week was 29 points, and the sum of the points of the lessons on Thursday was 30 points. On Thursday, it is necessary to replace the second lesson with the 5th lesson.

Lesson 3 on Friday is unevenly distributed in terms of difficulty, with a total of 27 points[3,4].

On Saturday, the total weight is 30 points, and the subject in lessons 1-2, which is difficult to master, should be moved to Wednesday or Thursday of the week.

6 "A" on Monday, the level of complexity of general lessons was 38 points, which does not meet hygienic requirements at all. If the complex lessons of 1, 2, 3 and 5 hours on Saturday are not changed to other days of the week, the students' ability to work will be reduced and the dynamic and statistical components of the lessons will be lost.

9 The level of complexity of classes in class "A" was 41-43-52-38-32-41 points. On Fridays, the daily load is 5-6 hours, so there are some disadvantages. It is necessary to replace the second hour classes on Saturday with other hours.

It is worth noting that the rough changes on Mondays and Saturdays of the week in this class cause changes in children's functional state, especially in their mental system, in the transition period of this age, not only in subjects, but also in their general interests. will be

Summary

1. Many scientific studies conducted in our country, as well as in foreign countries, in order to evaluate the impact of eating habits, behavior and culture on the growth and development of children and adolescents in the normal state, determine the optimal day for schoolchildren. it is necessary to focus on organizing and following a routine, organizing a healthy diet and ensuring optimal physical activity

2. The order and structure of the shifts of primary, middle and upper classes in the school do not comply with hygienic requirements, the options for breaks are completely derailed and do not comply with the specified hygienic requirements.

3. High school classes in 5th-6th-7th grade also have sharp inconsistencies, Mondays and Saturdays, difficult classes in the first and last hours during the week, conditions are created to create exhaustion of students during the day.

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